

STUDYING INTELLIGENCE IN PEDAGOGY**Ergasheva Dilnoza Toxirova SamSFL.****Shamsiddinov Murod Zubaydullayevich SamSFL.**

Annotation: This article devoted to open the theme studying intelligence in pedagogy and general characteristics of Intelligence. On the other hand, types of Intelligence and Theories of Intelligence were analyzed.

Key words: *environmental adjustment, language ability, academic performance, foster parents, Longitudinal studies, predictive effect, Abstract Intelligence.*

“Intelligence is the aggregate or global capacity of an individual to act purposefully, to think rationally and to deal effectively with his environment.” General characteristics of Intelligence : - imitating, talking ability, numerical ability, transfer of knowledge, environmental adjustment, language ability, learning ability, implicating, global, effective, number, creativeness and evaluation ability. The relationship between intelligence and education is one that scientists have been studying for years. Typically if maternal and paternal IQ is high, it is very likely for the child to have a high IQ as well. A study conducted by Plug and Vijverberg showed that the environment that a child grows up in also affects his or her future academic performance[1]. The children that were raised by their biological parents had a greater similarity in terms of intelligence and academic performance to their families than those raised by foster parents. Another study was conducted by Campbell and Ramey to test the socioeconomic effect on intelligence and it showed promising results for children at high risk of academic failure when there was an early intervention[2]. Longitudinal studies

have shown a predictive interaction of intelligence on educational attainment. In one study which measured around 70,000 children in the UK, they investigated how a general factor in the Cognitive Abilities Test taken at age 11 correlated with GCSE scores taken at age 16. They found that the two measures correlated about 0.8 with each other, showing intelligence at age 11 is predictive of grades at age 16. In this instance, children had received the same level of education, suggesting the variance is explained primarily by differences in intelligence rather than education. The predictive effect of IQ on educational success is even apparent if IQ is measured before any formal education, with measured correlations of IQ at the beginning of education and educational attainment six year later correlating 0.46. There are some main types of Intelligence :-

1. Abstract Intelligence :- The function of abstract intelligence is to solve subtle or abstract questions through reasoning and reflection. It brings the maximum possible clarity to concepts related to specific problems and experiences. Poets, men of literature, artists and others express their feelings through the use of this form of intelligence. This form of intelligence makes extensive use of words, numbers and symbols. It is the process of learning lessons or classroom materials : it is also the process of solving problems involving the use of words or symbols. It is for the reason that the ability to express one's thoughts is provided by the abstract intelligence through the medium of words and symbols. The development of abstract intelligence is very important in the school where such subjects as reading, mathematics, geography, history etc; are taught.
2. Concrete Intelligence :- Concrete- intelligence comes into play in the comprehending objects and then responding to them or performing activities related to them. The term "mechanical intelligence" and "motor intelligence" has also been used for this kind of intelligence.
3. Social Intelligence :- Social intelligence is that part of the individual's mental ability which generates in him the capacity to adapt himself to society[3].

Theories of Intelligence:-

(1) Unitary or Monarchic Theory : - Ross says that, intelligence is inborn and innate. This theory accepted intelligence as a part of body. This is a central point which generates all the mental activities.

(2) The Two Factor Theory (Electic Theory) :- Spearman propogated this theory. According to him, there are two elements in intelligence – (i) general ability (ii) specific ability. General ability is applied in every intellectual activity, and it differs from individual to individual, since very individual differs from another from the viewpoint of mental qualities. As far as specific ability is concerned, it too, differs from individual to individual. It makes its contribution to the individual's personal development and to the development of concepts.

(3) Multi-Factor Theory:- According to the theory, propogated by Thomdike, there is no such element as a general factor in intelligence. Intelligence is a compound of many factors, because any mental activity is performed by the collective functioning of many factors. It is for this reason that corelation can be found into mental tests. Thomdike has sought to throw light on the nature of intelligence on the basis of theory of stimulus - response. His view is that the experiences, between which the relationship of stimulus and response is established, help the individual to solve similar problems in the future.

(4) Group Factor Theory :- It is held in this theory propounded by Thurston that intelligence is a collectivity, congregation, aggregate of many factors, which he calls the group factors : -

1. Primary factors - According to Thurston, the primary factors in intelligence are the following :

(i) Number - The ability related to numbers helps in solving numerical or mathematical problems.

(ii) Verbal compherension - This is helpful in the development of logical thinking,

scholarly studies, knowledge of words, etc.

(iii) Space - This is essential for the perception of differences and distances, etc.

(iv) Word fluency - As a result of this ability, students develop capacity in the use of language,

(v) Reasoning - Though the medium of this ability, the student's capacity of reasoning is tested.

(vi) Rote memory - This indicates the individual's capacity for rote learning,

(vii) Perception

2. Secondary factors- This class included the following factors :

(i) Spatial ability - This is of use in discovering the special relations between objects.

(ii) Perceptual speed - This manifests the individual's speed in understanding an object or seeing it, observing its similarity to other objects and comprehending its difference to other objects.

(iii) Associative memory - The ability to remember two associated experiences falls in the sphere of this ability.

(iv) Problem solving - In the context of this ability, the individual's ability to solve new problem is tested.

The military provides a natural example of how those with lower intelligence learn less effectively and benefit less from education. The effect has been demonstrated as far back as World War II in which military fighter pilots were divided into groups based on a selection battery which included ability and motivation measures. Those who were in the top group completed training the first time 95% of the time, whereas those in the bottom group only completed training 20% the first time. Examples of low level recruits have even led to disagreement over whether these men should be enlisted at all, as they are costly to train, perform at a lower level than average when trained, and simply cannot learn certain specialties. Even those in favor of hiring those who are less

intelligent to the military acknowledge the limitations of these particular recruits, and instead try to get around the issue by adapting the training to cater for the mental ability of the less intelligent recruits[4]. These findings demonstrate how intelligence is necessary for learning and any form of training, and that those who are more intelligent learn more rapidly and effectively than those who are less intelligent. This could explain the high correlations between intelligence and educational attainment

Evidence shows that education and intelligence have a complex interaction, and this is demonstrated in a longitudinal study by Richards and Sacker. They collected data from the British 1946 birth cohort and investigated how childhood intelligence was predictive of other outcomes later in life including educational attainment and mental ability at 53 years old (using the National Adult Reading Test). The results of the experiment produced a path model in which mental ability at 8 years old was predictive of both educational attainment by 26, and mental ability at age 53. And also, education was shown to be predictive of mental ability at age 53. The findings show that intelligence at 8 years old is directly related to intelligence in later life. There is also, however, a mediating effect of education between the two intelligence measures, showing how education can have a positive effect on intelligence. This effect, however, appears to be limited by the stronger effect of initial intelligence. The Critical Thinking project at Human Science Lab, London, is involved in scientific study of all major educational systems in prevalence today to assess how the systems are working to promote or impede critical thinking and intelligence.

To sum up all given facts above it should be noted that the educational system of general secondary schools of Uzbekistan is a pedagogical process of educating students with social competences based on the specific national character of the Uzbek people, moral rules and the educational requirements of national independence. These scientific analyzes today put on the agenda the issue

of creating a scientific basis of effective propaganda methods in a new style, which rely on the support of new innovative, optimal, information technologies for the formation of social competences of students and young people. The growth of mental intelligence alone is not enough for the psychological maturity of students. In the formation of a specialist, each student is not only a subject capable of acquiring the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications for his field, but also a psychologically mature person who is flexible in social relations, able to feel the experiences of others, influence them, enter into relationships, adapt his behavior to others.

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